

Vulnerability Classification on Source Code using Text Mining and Deep Learning Techniques

Ilias Kalouptsoglou^{1,2,*}, Miltiadis Siavvas¹, Apostolos Ampatzoglou²,
Dionysios Kehagias¹, and Alexander Chatzigeorgiou²

¹Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Thessaloniki, Greece

²University of Macedonia, Thessaloniki, Greece

iliaskaloup@iti.gr, siavvasm@iti.gr, a.ampatzoglou@uom.edu.gr,

diok@iti.gr, achat@uom.edu.gr

*corresponding author

Abstract—Nowadays, security testing is an integral part of the testing activities during the software development life-cycle. Over the years, various techniques have been proposed to identify security issues in the source code, especially vulnerabilities, which can be exploited and cause severe damages. Recently, Machine Learning (ML) techniques capable of predicting vulnerable software components and indicating high-risk areas have appeared, among others, accelerating the effort demanding and time consuming process of vulnerability localization. For effective subsequent vulnerability elimination, there is a need for automating the process of labeling detected vulnerabilities in vulnerability categories i.e., identifying the type of the vulnerability. Several techniques have been proposed over the years for automating the labeling process of vulnerabilities. However, the vast majority of the proposed methods attempt to identify the type of vulnerabilities based on their textual description that is provided by experts, such as the description provided by the vulnerability report in the National Vulnerability Database, and not on their actual source code, hindering their full automation and the vulnerability categorization from the software testing phase. This work examines the vulnerability classification directly from the source code during the vulnerability detection step. Moreover, this way, a vulnerability detection method will be able to provide complete information and interpretation of its findings. Leveraging the advances in the field of Artificial Intelligence and Natural Language Processing, we construct and compare several multi-class classification models for categorizing vulnerable code snippets. The results highlight the importance of the context-aware embeddings of the pre-trained Transformer-based models, as well as the significance of transfer learning from a programming language-related domain.

Index Terms—security testing; vulnerability classification; natural language processing; contextual word embedding; large language models; transfer learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Software security holds a crucial role in the software development life-cycle (SDLC), as described in the International Standard on Software Quality ISO/IEC 25010 [1]. A primary concern of the software community is the identification, characterisation and mitigation of vulnerabilities present in the source code. These vulnerabilities represent weaknesses in software systems that external threats could exploit [2][3]. Prior to the release of any software product, it is essential to conduct thorough security testing, with particular emphasis on the use of vulnerability detection tools. By employing such mechanisms, software organisations can efficiently allocate

their resources and efforts to strengthen potentially vulnerable components.

As modern software systems become more complex and interconnected, there is a constantly increasing number of new identified vulnerabilities [4]. Thus, there is a need for a classification scheme to group related and similar vulnerabilities. Therefore, the Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) system [5] was introduced by MITRE to categorize weaknesses found in software systems. Each individual CWE represents a single vulnerability type. However, CWE is an expert-based system, where those who found a vulnerability are often different from the categorizers of it [6]. Moreover, the aforementioned manual categorization usually is a time consuming procedure. According to Spanos et al. [7], there are delays between when a vulnerability is reported, when the technical description is conducted, and when the vulnerability is characterized with a CWE and a severity score.

Recently, approaches of employing Machine Learning (ML) algorithms for automating the procedure of categorizing vulnerabilities have appeared. To enhance the manual classification carried out by the security experts, Aivatoglou et al. used ML to categorize reported vulnerabilities into CWEs utilizing the textual descriptions provided from NVD for each vulnerability [8]. Additionally, Liu et al. classified vulnerabilities gathered from cybersecurity articles and websites into the groups of code injection, access issues, buff errors, and SQL injection [9]. However, although these approaches may automate the categorization of the already reported vulnerabilities, they still need a formal and accurate vulnerability-specific technical description to be written in textual form by an expert first. In other words, none of these methods are part of software testing, since they utilize vulnerability-related meta-data instead of information retrieved from the analyzed source code itself.

In contrast with vulnerability prediction techniques, which are commonly built based on ML models that utilize software attributes to predict vulnerable hot-spots (e.g., files, classes, methods, etc.) in a software product [10][11][12], the procedure of labeling the predicted vulnerabilities is currently disconnected from the software testing phase, raising questions about the interpretability, and hence, the reliability of the findings of the testing activities. ML-enabled vulnerability

prediction has grown significantly, but it still presents important drawbacks, which stand as obstacles for its adoption in practice. For instance, although it overcomes the limitations of static analysis by producing much fewer false positives and being able to identify not only coding violations of pre-defined rules but also complex vulnerability patterns that cannot be expressed in the form of static analysis rules [13][14], it lacks the ability of static code analyzers to present specific lines and categories of the security alerts [15].

In simple words, vulnerability prediction models are able to highlight software components that are likely to be vulnerable, but they typically do not provide information about the type and the exact location of the potential vulnerability, leaving a lot of manual work to the engineers. Knowing at least the type of the vulnerability would greatly help the development team, as it would narrow down their focus to specific security weaknesses, allowing them to employ dedicated testing techniques and test cases that are more effective for this type of issue.

Recent research endeavors in the field of software vulnerability prediction have attempted to reduce the level of granularity of their predictions, focusing on localizing as much as possible the vulnerable lines of code per component [16][17]. For this purpose, they often employ explainable Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods (e.g., Attention mechanism) in order to recognize the parts of the code that were the most important in the model's prediction of a vulnerability. However, these techniques do not provide further information about the category of the vulnerability, since they try to explain the model's decision of classifying a file or a function as vulnerable in a binary classification scheme.

The purpose of this study is to present a mechanism of classifying detected vulnerabilities, providing this way developers with valuable insights into the kind of the security issues that exist in their software (e.g., Command Injection, Deadlock, SQL Injection, etc.) during the testing phase of the SDLC when the vulnerabilities are actually identified. To this end, we conduct an extensive comparative analysis of several Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques applied in the textual format of vulnerable source code snippets.

In particular, we examine two different text representations methods (i) Bag-of-Words (BoW) and (ii) sequences of tokens as well as four different word embedding algorithms (i) Word2vec [18], (ii) fastText [19], (iii) Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [20], and (iv) CodeBERT [21]. We also train different kinds of ML models (e.g., Random Forest, Support Vector Machines, and Transformer). Furthermore, special attention is paid on the adoption of transfer learning. Last but not least, we provide insightful observations for the strengths and the weaknesses of each examined algorithm based on the results.

The rest of the paper comprise five main sections. Section 2 provides an overview of the state-of-the-art methods for categorizing vulnerabilities, while Section 3 presents the relevant theoretical framework for the text mining techniques under examination. Section 4 describes the utilized dataset,

the machine learning algorithms, and the overall methodology of this study. The findings of our evaluation approach are presented and discussed in Section 5, and Section 6 provides the conclusions of the study along with directions for future research.

2. RELATED WORK

Research studies about the characterization of security vulnerabilities focused on the technical description provided for the reported software flaws in textual form. Initially, Neuhaus and Zimmermann analyzed vulnerability reports in the CVE database, represented as BoW, utilizing an unsupervised ML algorithm (i.e., Latent Dirichlet Allocation) to find the most usual types of vulnerability [22].

Then, Yamamoto et al. developed a method able to calculate vulnerability scores based on the natural language description provided by CVE [23], while Wen et al. proposed an automatic vulnerability categorization framework using text mining on the vulnerability descriptions in NVD [6]. Subsequently, Aghaei et al. presented ThreatZoom, a tool capable of classifying CVEs into CWEs from CVE descriptions using Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) [24].

Furthermore, Yosifova et al. examined the performance of several baseline ML models on predicting the vulnerability type using as features the CVE descriptions [25]. In addition, Aivatoglou et al. proposed a text analysis and ML-based method to automate the process of vulnerability classification using NVD descriptions, showcasing the high prediction accuracy of tree-based models [8].

In the vulnerability prediction-related literature, where studies utilize software attributes to classify software components as vulnerable or not, text mining techniques have demonstrated encouraging results [11][26][27][28]. However, a very limited number of studies has dealt with the objective of classifying vulnerabilities to vulnerability categories as highlighted in a systematic mapping study on software vulnerability prediction [29].

Siavvas et al. observed that software metrics are not sufficient indicators of specific vulnerability types [30]. Then Wartschinski et al. proposed VUDENC, which is a Deep Learning (DL) and text mining-based vulnerability detection model [31] that considers several different vulnerability categories. Although in their study they presented also results per vulnerability category, they focused on identifying which components are vulnerable, by performing binary classification. Moreover, Kong et al. dealt with the problem of identifying multi-type vulnerabilities, using graph embeddings and graph neural networks, but, although they included several CWEs in their dataset, they also focused on the discrimination between vulnerable and non-vulnerable components [32]. In fact, they were more interested in exploring how best to capture the diverse code representations of different types of vulnerabilities.

One of the initial attempts to classify software vulnerabilities during the security testing phase is [33], where the authors noticed the need for pinpointing types of vulnerabilities during

their detection phase. They proposed the use of DL, Bidirectional Long-Short Time Memory (BiLSTM) neural network specifically, to implement a multi-class vulnerability prediction model. They also noticed that training a separate model for each type of vulnerabilities and apply all of them to every single sample of the testing data is neither a scalable nor an effective enough solution.

Next, Mamede et al. explored the capabilities of Transformer-based models on the classification of software vulnerabilities [34]. Particularly, they trained several BERT variants for multi-label vulnerability classification using a synthetic dataset of Java source code. Moreover, Mazuera-Rozo et al. examined several different source code representations and ML classifiers in both binary and multi-class vulnerability prediction in function-level of granularity, showing a very high accuracy drop in both cases when using real-world data instead of synthetic ones [35].

From the above analysis, we can argue that there is a lack of fine-grained vulnerability classification mechanisms, operating in the testing phase of the SDLC. Moreover, existing methods have focused primarily on C/C++ and secondary on Java vulnerabilities. The most promising work seems to be the study of Zou et al. but their study [33] has several limitations, since it: (i) identifies solely vulnerabilities related to API/library function calls, (ii) cannot localize the identified vulnerabilities, (iii) is based on a dataset that is largely synthetic, and (iv) deals only with C/C++ code.

In the present study, we propose a method that enhances the automation of the vulnerabilities' categorization as opposed to the traditional expert-based labeling, by leveraging AI and NLP algorithms. Concisely, the contributions of the mechanism presented in this study to the relevant literature can be summarised as follows: Firstly, this mechanism achieves classification of vulnerabilities from the early phase of security testing as opposed to other ML-based methods that classify reported vulnerabilities based on their description provided by NVD [8][9]. Secondly, the proposed scheme provides increased confidence in the security test findings by complementing vulnerability predictions with the categories of the identified vulnerabilities.

In addition, this study categorizes vulnerable lines of code, and hence, achieves a lower level of granularity of the vulnerability classification process, as opposed to studies that use the source code to implement multi-class vulnerability prediction by predicting which files or methods contain vulnerabilities and of what kind [33][34][35]. Actually, to the best of our knowledge, the present study is the first to delve into the classification of specific vulnerable lines of code to vulnerability categories, by examining and comparing several different embedding algorithms and NLP models.

Moreover, we classify real-world vulnerabilities (instead of synthetic ones), which belong to categories of vulnerabilities (e.g., Command Injection, Path Disclosure, Open Redirect, etc.) that are considered major security issues in software engineering. Furthermore, this study performs vulnerability classification on source code written in Python, which is

one of the fastest growing and most popular programming languages [36], but not so much explored in this field. Finally, a discussion is conducted regarding the relationship between the results obtained and the differences, as well as the technological developments in the NLP techniques considered.

3. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In this section, a description of the main text mining techniques utilized in the current study is provided. In particular, details about the main concepts that we adopted from the NLP domain to perform vulnerability classification are presented. To train ML models to classify vulnerabilities based on code snippets identified as vulnerable, we first needed to represent the source code in a numerical way. For this purpose, we used common textual representation methods. In particular, we used (i) Bag-of-Words (BoW) and (ii) sequences of tokens representations.

On the one hand, BoW is the simplest NLP method that allows training ML models on text data. In the BoW approach, code snippets are collected in a "bag" that contains the words of each snippet, without considering their sequential order. This method constructs a vocabulary from the words of the entire training dataset, with each code snippet represented as a vector aligned with the vocabulary. The values of this vector are the number of occurrences of each word in the code snippet. This way, the textual data of the code snippets are transformed to tabular data, allowing the code to be analyzed through a structured numerical format.

On the other hand, in the sequences of tokens approach, each code snippet is represented as a sequence of the words included in the snippet. Therefore, the sequential order of the tokens within the code snippets is preserved, giving a benefit to ML algorithms that are capable of capturing the structural dependencies hidden among the tokens of the source code. After constructing token sequences, a word embedding method has to be applied in order to feed ML models with numerical vectors, as well as to represent better the meaning of the words.

In order to vectorize the sequences of tokens, we employed various sophisticated word embedding algorithms, such as Word2vec and fastText, as well as the word embeddings provided by Transformers. These algorithms are DL models capable of learning semantic and syntactic relationships among the tokens and place them at the vector space based on their similarity. More specifically, words that are close to each other in the text (i.e. in the source code) are also placed close to each other in the vector space.

Word2vec, which was initially proposed by Mikolov et al. and Google [18], is one of the most popular and widely used techniques for vectorizing source code [37][38][39]. This method employs two primary architectures, namely the Continuous Bag-of-Words (CBOW) and Skip-gram [18]. The first aims at predicting a target word based on the words of its context in a sentence, whereas the latter aims at predicting context words based on a target word. Although Word2vec has proved to be efficient in a variety of NLP tasks [40], it has several drawbacks, as well. Specifically, it neither

handles the out-of-vocabulary (OOV) problem nor is able to capture contextual relationships of the words. In other words, Word2vec assigns unique and global embeddings to the words regardless of their context.

To the contrary, fastText, which is another efficient word embedding algorithm proposed by Bojanowski et al. and Facebook AI [19], manages to handle the OOV problem by considering sub-word information. More specifically, fastText breaks words into smaller units, such as character n-grams, and therefore, is able to handle OOV words. Similarly to Word2vec, it has both CBOW and Skip-gram architectures. However, it still has difficulty in understanding the complex semantic relationships and multiple meanings of words. Therefore, both fastText and Word2vec embeddings are called static or global embeddings as they are unique per word and do not change based on the context.

A more evolved architecture namely the Transformer, which was originally proposed by Vaswani et al. and Google [41], managed to surpass the aforementioned issues of the traditional word embeddings techniques. Specifically, the Transformer architecture, which revolutionised the NLP field, introduced the positional embeddings that can capture relative positions of the tokens in the sequences. In other words, the Transformer, through its positional embeddings, can capture contextual patterns across the whole input sequence with positional information. Therefore, each word’s embedding vector is not unique but depends on the context. As opposed to the static vectors, Transformer-based word embeddings are considered contextual embeddings.

One popular model based on the Transformer architecture is the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) model that was proposed by Google [20]. It is an encoder-only Transformer, which has been pre-trained on the task of masked language modeling (MLM) using a large corpus consisted of English Wikipedia and BookCorpus [42]. More specifically, it was trained to predict the original tokens (i.e., words) in sentences where 15% of them were randomly masked by a special *mask* token. In a replication study of BERT, Liu et al. [43] observed that BERT was significantly undertrained, and therefore, they proposed a robustly optimized pre-training approach, called RoBERTa.

Based on the RoBERTa model, Microsoft pre-trained a model called CodeBERT [21], which is a bimodal model that has been pre-trained not only on natural language but also on six programming languages (i.e., Java, Python, Go, Ruby, PHP, and JavaScript). In particular, Feng et al. pre-trained it in pairs of function-level source code and the corresponding documentation in natural language. During pre-training, CodeBERT learnt general-purpose representations that proved to be useful in tasks such as generation of code documentation and code search based on natural language queries [21]. It is worth noting that BERT and its variants have been widely used in various software engineering tasks, ranging from software requirements extraction to requirements classification and vulnerability repair demonstrating remarkable capabilities [44][45][46].

TABLE I
DATASET CLASS DISTRIBUTION

Vulnerability category	No. of vulnerabilities
SQL Injection	1431
XSRF	976
Command Injection	721
Path Disclosure	481
Open Redirect	442
Remote Code Execution	334
XSS	145

4. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the overall methodology that we followed in order to predict the types of software vulnerabilities. In particular, we present the dataset utilized, the strategy of constructing ML models, and the evaluation procedure. Figure 1 illustrates all the steps of our experimental setup: (i) data collection and preparation, (ii) model selection and training setup, (iii) model training, parameterization and prediction, and (iv) model evaluation and comparison.

4.1 Dataset

For training and evaluating the examined vulnerability classification approaches, we utilized a dataset that consists of Python source code. This dataset is provided by Wartschinski et al. [31], who employed a version control system namely as GitHub as a data source for gathering software components. To construct a dataset containing files labeled to indicate their vulnerability status (i.e., vulnerable or not), they analyzed numerous commit messages from Python programming language projects hosted on GitHub.

They specifically went through commits with keywords in the commit messages that were indicative of a vulnerability fix. They accumulated a large number of Python source files related to these commits. The parent version of each file that existed before the vulnerability-fixing commit was flagged as vulnerable because it contained the vulnerability that needed to be fixed. They also collected the *diff* files, which list the source code-level changes made between two successive commits. Thus, they were able to extract the exact lines that were repaired and therefore to determine which lines were vulnerable.

All those collected vulnerable block of lines were also characterized by a unique vulnerability category. This specific labeling was conducted based on the keywords included in the commit messages of the fixing commits. The authors of [31] chose to include keywords indicative of seven common vulnerability types, taking into account the OWASP Top 10 list [47]. Specifically, the dataset contains 4530 code blocks categorized as SQL Injection, Cross-Site Request Forgery (XSRF), Command Injection, Path Disclosure, Open Redirect, Remote Code Execution, and Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) vulnerabilities. Table I presents the distribution of the classes (i.e., vulnerability categories) in the dataset.

4.2 Study Design

In the first step of our methodology, after retrieving the vulnerability-related data, we pre-processed the code snippets. Specifically, we substituted all numerical constants such as integers, floats, etc. and string literals with two distinct identifiers, "numId\$" and "strId\$" correspondingly. This substitution made the code snippets more abstract and independent of application-specific constants, which might otherwise impact the performance of the models.

Subsequently, in the model selection phase, we represented the source code in two formats namely as BoW and sequences of tokens. The former is in numerical form as it represents the source code in a table of words with their number of occurrences as features. For the latter, we transformed each sequence to a numerical vector called embedding, comparing several embedding methods (i.e., Word2vec, fastText, BERT, and CodeBERT). For the actual implementation of these techniques, we employed the algorithms provided by Gensim¹ and Hugging Face² libraries for the global and contextual embeddings respectively.

For the cases of Word2vec and fastText (i.e., global embeddings), since we deal with a programming language-related task, we trained word embedding vectors leveraging a large code corpus that is provided by Wartschinski et al. [48]. This corpus consists of functions written in Python programming language and it contains 11.5 million lines of code in total. Then we computed the mean among the embedding vectors that correspond to the different words in each input sequence, resulting in a single vector that represents the average of all the word vectors in the sequence.

On the other hand, for the case of Transformer-based models, there was no need for training embedding vectors as they are models already pre-trained on large datasets. Therefore, we utilized the pre-trained models provided by Hugging Face. In addition, in this case, we fed the sequences of tokens to the pre-trained models in inference mode and we extracted the sentence-level embedding vectors from the last hidden state of the Transformer. This way we gained a contextual embedding vector for each sequence of tokens given as input.

Furthermore, either the BoW or the embedding vectors of the sequences were fed to a ML model in order to perform multi-class classification to vulnerability categories. For the selection of the classifier, we examined several ML models including Decision Trees (DT), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Random Forest (RF) classifiers. We also examined the approach of fine-tuning the pre-trained BERT and CodeBERT models to the downstream task of vulnerability category prediction.

As opposed to the embeddings extraction approach, during fine-tuning the whole model participates in the training to the downstream task. Regarding the Transformer-based models utilized (i.e., BERT and CodeBERT), we leveraged the pre-trained models that are provided by Hugging Face. In partic-

ular, the *bert-base* model, which has 110 millions parameters, 12 layers of 768 size, and 12 attention heads [41] was utilized, whereas for CodeBERT we leveraged the *codebert-base-mlm* version, which, similarly with *roberta-base*, has the BERT architecture but 125M parameters.

In step 3 of Figure 1, we trained the aforementioned models using the training set of the dataset. We have to clarify that we conducted several experiments until ending up with the optimal hyperparameters. For the training of the static word embedding using a python code corpus, we utilized a vector dimension equal to 100 and a context window size of 20 words. As embedding architectures, we used Skip-gram and CBOW for Word2vec and fastText respectively. Regarding the ML classifiers, for RF we used 100 decision trees using bootstrap sampling and the square root of the total number of features at each split. For DT model, the tree was selected to grow until it reaches a maximum depth of 120 levels, while the SVM utilized a radial basis kernel and a gamma value equal to 100. Interestingly, KNN ended up with a single neighbor.

Furthermore, BERT and CodeBERT were fine-tuned with a learning rate equal with 0.00005, Adam optimizer, and maximum length of the input sequences defined as 512, which is the maximum length that they can support. To determine the number of epochs the early stopping technique was utilized with 100 maximum epochs and a patience of 5 consecutive epochs without improvement. Moreover, during the tokenization of the textual data with BERT and CodeBERT, zero padding was applied to make all the sequence to have the same length and also the truncation technique was employed to cut-off sequences longer than the maximum length.

Then we utilized the optimised models to predict vulnerability categories for the code snippets that comprise the unseen testing set. Finally, in step 4, we evaluated the optimised models of all the different approaches using common classification metrics to measure their predictive performance on the test data. Therefore, we managed to compare those approaches and to identify which method achieves the highest accuracy scores.

4.3 Evaluation Scheme

To evaluate the models that we trained in the task of vulnerability classification, we applied the well established technique called k-fold cross-validation [29]. During this process, the dataset is separated in k different parts, specifically for the purpose of our experiment in ten folds. Then, the nine folds are utilized as training set and the rest one as testing set. The training and testing is repeated ten times, each time selecting a different fold as the test set. This way, we avoid putting data bias on the developed models, assuring that the models can perform well on various parts of the dataset and not on one random split.

As regards the measurement of the performance of the models, we utilized the accuracy, precision (P), recall (R), and F₁-score classification metrics, which are frequently utilized in the literature [8][29]. The value of these metrics is determined from the number of True Positives (TP), True Negatives

¹<https://radimrehurek.com/gensim/>

²<https://huggingface.co/>

Fig. 1. Overview of the overall approach.

(TN), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN) that are produced by the models. For facilitating the comparison among the examined techniques, we pay more attention on the F_1 -score, which considers both precision and recall giving equal weight to them, and therefore, is most suitable for evaluating these models. On the contrary, we do not pay so much attention on accuracy, since our dataset is imbalanced and therefore accuracy could be misleading.

We have to clarify also that we present the macro average values of the aforementioned metrics, instead of micro or weighted average. Macro averaging is equal to the arithmetic mean of all the per-class scores, without using any class weights for the aggregation. To the contrary, weighted averaging, for instance, of F_1 -score, calculates all the per-class F_1 -scores but when adding them, it uses a weight depending on the number of true labels of every class, whereas micro averaging computes TP, FP, TN, and FN separately for every class and then computes the global F_1 -score [49]. Since we consider all classes equally important, and therefore, we do not have to take into account the number of samples per class, we qualify the macro averaging method. Equations (1), (2), and (3) present the mathematical formulas of the macro average values of recall, precision, and F_1 -score respectively.

$$R = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Ri = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{TPi}{TPi + FNi} \quad (1)$$

$$P = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Pi = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{TPi}{TPi + FPi} \quad (2)$$

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N F_{1i} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{2 \times Pi \times Ri}{Pi + Ri} = \quad (3)$$

, where i is the index of each class.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section we present the findings of our experimental analysis. The experiments were held on a GeForce RTX 3060 Nvidia GPU with a parallel computing platform called CUDA³ installed. For the implementation of the DL algorithms we used the TensorFlow⁴ platform, while for the ML classification models, we utilized the scikit-learn⁵ library. To enhance the reproducibility of the experiments, we provide our scripts online [50].

Initially, an empirical comparison of several ML classifiers (i.e., Decision Trees, Support Vector Machines, KNN, and Random Forest) was conducted so as to identify the best performing one for each utilized token numerical representation technique (i.e., BoW, Word2vec, fastText, BERT, and CodeBERT). Figure 2 provides a bar chart that shows the F_1 -scores of all the examined models.

As can be seen, Decision Tree (DT) is the less accurate model regardless of the NLP method, whereas the Random Forest (RF) achieves the highest scores. The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) models are the second and third best models in all cases, with

³<https://developer.nvidia.com/cuda-toolkit>

⁴<https://www.tensorflow.org/>

⁵<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

Fig. 2. Comparison of different ML classification models per NLP approach.

one outperforming the other in some cases and vice versa. Therefore, we can argue that RF, which is an Ensemble model which combines the output of several decision trees [51], is superior than the other examined classifiers. Hence, we qualify it as our predictor in the subsequent experiments.

Regarding the comparison among the NLP method utilized for text representation, in Table II the macro average values of the classification metrics achieved by the best performing ML model (i.e., Random Forest) are presented. We can see that all of the examined methods achieve adequate prediction performance with F_1 -scores above 75% except for Word2vec, which suffers from the OOV problem and also does not consider the context of each token when representing it with a numerical vector.

To the contrary, fastText operates on character and sub-word level, and therefore, it can represent efficiently OOV tokens. However, it still overlooks the context of tokens in different sequences. This is where BERT excels, since it provides context-aware embeddings, managing to outperform Word2vec by almost 10%, but it lacks knowledge of the programming language. The BERT variant called CodeBERT is a method that encompasses all the aforementioned concepts as it is context-aware (like BERT), handles OOV problem using sub-word tokenization (similarly to fastText), and has prior knowledge of programming languages.

The findings presented in Table II show that the OOV problem is a significant one, resulting in low performance by Word2vec. Furthermore, fastText managed to surpass the context-aware BERT highlighting the importance of having domain-specific prior knowledge (i.e., programming language). Moreover, the fact that fastText and CodeBERT are

very close not only to each other but also to BoW, with BoW actually to be a bit higher, suggests that the classification process may pay more attention to the occurrence in the code snippets of specific tokens that are indicative of a vulnerability category, and, to the contrary, may have difficulty in capturing syntactic patterns that reside in the source code.

Subsequently, in order to depict clearer the role of the prior knowledge in transfer learning-based vulnerability classification, we present Table III. On the one hand, Table III contains the classification scores of our approach when using pre-trained Word2vec, fastText, and BERT embeddings. These pre-trained embeddings have been trained on large corpuses of natural language and have learnt syntactics and semantics of words. Word2vec was originally pre-trained on a dataset of google news, while fastText was pre-trained on Wikipedia data and BERT on a dataset comprising English Wikipedia and BookCorpus⁶. On the other hand, Table III presents the classification scores for Word2vec and fastText embeddings that we trained using a Python corpus, and also for the CodeBERT which is already pre-trained on programming languages-related data.

Based on the findings presented in Table III, it is clear that in all cases the prior knowledge of domain-specific language (i.e., programming language) is very beneficial in the task of vulnerability classification. In particular, we can see that when representing code snippets with code-aware embeddings, we succeed higher scores in all of accuracy, precision, recall, and F_1 -score metrics.

Furthermore, we proceeded with training the whole

⁶<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BookCorpus>

TABLE II
EVALUATION RESULTS OF THE RANDOM FOREST CLASSIFIER PER TEXT VECTORIZING METHOD

Vectorizing Method	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F ₁ -score (%)
Bag-of-Words	81.9	82.3	77.2	79.1
Word2vec	71.6	76.2	64.3	68.0
fastText	80.2	84.0	73.9	77.7
BERT	76.9	86.6	69.4	75.1
CodeBERT	80.7	87.6	72.9	78.0

TABLE III
CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE OF NLP MODELS WITH PRIOR KNOWLEDGE OF NATURAL LANGUAGE VERSUS PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE

Vectorizing Method	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F ₁ -score (%)
pre-trained Word2vec	68.1	73.2	59.9	63.8
re-trained Word2vec	71.6	76.2	64.3	68.0
pre-trained fastText	74.9	78.0	68.0	71.5
re-trained fastText	80.2	84.0	73.9	77.7
pre-trained BERT	76.9	86.6	69.4	75.1
pre-trained CodeBERT	80.7	87.6	72.9	78.0

TABLE IV
COMPARISON OF EMBEDDINGS EXTRACTION AND FINE-TUNING OF TRANSFORMER MODELS APPROACHES

Vectorizing Method	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F ₁ -score (%)
BERT + RF	76.9	86.6	69.4	75.1
BERT fine-tuning	84.5	82.4	82.7	82.5
CodeBERT + RF	80.7	87.6	72.9	78.0
CodeBERT fine-tuning	87.4	86.3	85.2	85.5

Transformer-based models. More specifically, instead of extracting their embeddings and feeding them to the ML classifiers, we fine-tuned BERT and CodeBERT models on the downstream task of vulnerability classification. Table IV compares the fine-tuning and embeddings extraction approaches of employing Large Language Models (LLMs).

By inspecting Table IV, we can see that when utilizing BERT embeddings with a RF classifier, the accuracy achieved is 76.9%, with corresponding precision, recall, and F₁-score of 86.6%, 69.4%, and 75.1%, respectively. However, fine-tuning BERT significantly improves results, with a significant boost in F₁-score from 75.1% to 82.5%. This improvement suggests that fine-tuning enables BERT to adapt better to the specific nuances of the downstream task, leading to enhanced predictive performance.

In addition, fine-tuned CodeBERT demonstrates higher scores than fine-tuned BERT, confirming the findings of Table III regarding the effectiveness of CodeBERT in capturing code-related features. Moreover, fine-tuning CodeBERT results in a substantial performance gain compared to the features (i.e., embeddings) extraction approach, achieving an F₁-score of 85.5%, which is by far the highest F₁-score reported in this study.

This improvement highlights the importance of fine-tuning pre-trained models, pointing the capability of the Transformer architecture to capture long-term dependencies that RF cannot. Hence, the fine-tuning approach seems to be the optimal one, at least for this specific objective (i.e., vulnerability classification), especially when working with domain-specific data (i.e.,

source code). All things considered, the results showcase (i) the benefit of performing fine-tuning over feature extraction in both BERT and CodeBERT cases, and (ii) the superiority of the fine-tuned CodeBERT over the fine-tuned BERT.

For reasons of completeness, at this point we provide the detailed results for each of the seven vulnerability categories achieved by each of the best performing vulnerability classification approaches. Specifically, Table V showcases the F₁-score of the fine-tuning CodeBERT, fine-tuning BERT, BoW, CodeBERT embeddings with ML classifier, and fastText embeddings with ML classifier approaches, which are the ones that achieved the highest F₁-score in order.

As presented in Table V, on the one hand, it seems that our best model, which is the fine-tuned CodeBERT, manages to classify effectively all the vulnerability categories included in the analysis. In particular, it achieves F₁-score 90% and above in the three most numerous categories (i.e., SQL Injection, XSRF, and Command Injection). It also succeeds high scores close to 90% in case of Path Disclosure and XSS, and over 80% even for the Remote Code Execution category, regardless the fact that XSS and Remote Code Execution categories have the less samples in the dataset (especially XSS). Only the prediction of Open Redirect has an F₁-score lower than 80%, but it still reaches 75%.

On the other hand, although it is clear that fine-tuned CodeBERT achieves not only higher average scores but also higher scores per category for most cases, there are some exceptions. In case of Open Redirect vulnerabilities, which is the most weak category of CodeBERT, there are other

TABLE V
F₁-SCORE PER CATEGORY OF THE FIVE BEST PERFORMING APPROACHES

Category	CodeBERT fine-tuning	BERT fine-tuning	BoW + RF	CodeBERT + RF	fastText + RF
SQL Injection	90	86	89	82	86
XSRF	90	91	86	86	80
Open Redirect	75	72	82	77	77
XSS	86	87	77	67	73
Remote Code Execution	81	71	86	80	81
Command Injection	91	86	77	85	81
Path Disclosure	87	85	68	72	79

approaches that achieve more accurate predictions. In particular, all BoW, fastText and CodeBERT with RF approaches surpass CodeBERT fine-tuning in classifying Open Redirect vulnerabilities. Especially, BoW seems to have a substantial benefit (i.e., 7% higher F₁-score). It also manages to surpass by 5% the fine-tuned CodeBERT in the Remote Code Execution classification, which is the second weakest category of the fine-tuned CodeBERT. Hence, the CodeBERT could be used as the main model for categorizing the detected vulnerabilities, and in case that the detected vulnerability is classified as Open Redirect (or Remote Code Execution), one could supplementarily utilize another model that has higher predictive performance in this category (e.g., the BoW with RF model in our case), to reach safer conclusions.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, our primary purpose was to categorize detected security vulnerabilities such as Path Disclosure, Command Injection, etc. from the testing phase of the SDLC, using source code attributes as features, as opposed to traditional techniques, which classify reported vulnerabilities based on descriptions provided by NVD. To this end, we leveraged several NLP text representation and text classification techniques adopting a multi-class classification procedure.

During the conducted investigation, we considered and compared two distinct approaches: (i) build traditional ML models based on numerical representations of vulnerable code snippets produced by a range of common NLP techniques (e.g., BoW, Word2vec, fastText, BERT, and CodeBERT), and (ii) build Transformer-based models through fine-tuning popular pre-trained models like BERT, and CodeBERT. The findings demonstrate the superiority of CodeBERT model, which is the one that handles the OOV issue using sub-tokenization, has domain-specific prior knowledge, and also has contextual understanding. The results show important benefit from fine-tuning over extracting embeddings approach, as well.

Several directions for future work can be defined. For instance, an interesting analysis could include the application of explainable AI techniques to reveal which parts of the code snippets were the most influential in the models' category predictions. Additionally, we aim at implementing a complete working prototype that will be able to parse the source code of software projects, identify vulnerable components, detect the specific code snippets that contain vulnerabilities, and then classify them to vulnerability categories.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Work reported in this paper has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program through the DOSS project, Grant Number 101120270.

REFERENCES

- [1] ISO/IEC, *ISO/IEC 25010 - Systems and software engineering - Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuARE) - System and software quality models*. ISO/IEC, 2011.
- [2] M. C. Sánchez, J. M. C. de Gea, J. L. Fernández-Alemán, J. Garcerán, and A. Toval, "Software vulnerabilities overview: A descriptive study," *Tsinghua Science and Technology*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 270–280, 2019.
- [3] ISO/IEC, *ISO/IEC 27000:2018 - Information technology — Security techniques — Information security management systems*. ISO/IEC, 2005.
- [4] "Cyber Crime & Security," <https://www.statista.com/statistics/500755/worldwide-common-vulnerabilities-and-exposures>, Accessed: 2024-03-15.
- [5] "Common Weakness Enumeration," <https://cwe.mitre.org/>, Accessed: 2024-03-15.
- [6] T. Wen, Y. Zhang, Q. Wu, and G. Yang, "Asvc: An automatic security vulnerability categorization framework based on novel features of vulnerability data." *J. Commun.*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 107–116, 2015.
- [7] G. Spanos and L. Angelis, "A multi-target approach to estimate software vulnerability characteristics and severity scores," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 146, pp. 152–166, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016421218302061>
- [8] G. Aivatoglou, M. Anastasiadis, G. Spanos, A. Voulgaridis, K. Votis, and D. Tzovaras, "A tree-based machine learning methodology to automatically classify software vulnerabilities," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (CSR)*, 2021, pp. 312–317.
- [9] C. Liu, J. Li, and X. Chen, "Network vulnerability analysis using text mining," in *Intelligent Information and Database Systems: 4th Asian Conference, ACIIDS 2012, Kaohsiung, Taiwan, March 19-21, 2012, Proceedings, Part II 4*. Springer, 2012, pp. 274–283.
- [10] R. Scandariato, J. Walden, A. Hovsepian, and W. Joosen, "Predicting vulnerable software components via text mining," *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. 40, no. 10, pp. 993–1006, 2014.
- [11] J. Walden, J. Stuckman, and R. Scandariato, "Predicting vulnerable components: Software metrics vs text mining," in *2014 IEEE 25th international symposium on software reliability engineering*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 23–33.
- [12] I. Kalouptsoglou, M. Siavvas, D. Tsoukalas, and D. Kehagias, "Cross-project vulnerability prediction based on software metrics and deep learning," in *International Conference on Computational Science and Its Applications*. Springer, 2020, pp. 877–893.
- [13] B. Johnson, Y. Song, E. Murphy-Hill, and R. Bowdidge, "Why don't software developers use static analysis tools to find bugs?" in *2013 35th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 672–681.
- [14] M. Siavvas, I. Kalouptsoglou, D. Tsoukalas, and D. Kehagias, "A self-adaptive approach for assessing the criticality of security-related static analysis alerts," in *Computational Science and Its Applications—ICCSA 2021: 21st International Conference, Cagliari, Italy, September 13–16, 2021, Proceedings, Part VII 21*. Springer, 2021, pp. 289–305.

- [15] M. Siavvas, D. Kehagias, D. Tzovaras, and E. Gelenbe, "A hierarchical model for quantifying software security based on static analysis alerts and software metrics," *Software Quality Journal*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 431–507, 2021.
- [16] Y. Li, S. Wang, and T. N. Nguyen, "Vulnerability detection with fine-grained interpretations," in *Proceedings of the 29th ACM Joint Meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering*, 2021, pp. 292–303.
- [17] F. Yang, F. Zhong, G. Zeng, P. Xiao, and W. Zheng, "Lineflowdp: A deep learning-based two-phase approach for line-level defect prediction," *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 1–49, 2024.
- [18] T. Mikolov, K. Chen, G. Corrado, and J. Dean, "Efficient estimation of word representations in vector space," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1301.3781*, 2013.
- [19] P. Bojanowski, E. Grave, A. Joulin, and T. Mikolov, "Enriching word vectors with subword information," *Transactions of the association for computational linguistics*, vol. 5, pp. 135–146, 2017.
- [20] J. Devlin, M.-W. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, "Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.04805*, 2018.
- [21] Z. Feng, D. Guo, D. Tang, N. Duan, X. Feng, M. Gong, L. Shou, B. Qin, T. Liu, D. Jiang *et al.*, "Codebert: A pre-trained model for programming and natural languages," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2002.08155*, 2020.
- [22] S. Neuhaus and T. Zimmermann, "Security trend analysis with cve topic models," in *2010 IEEE 21st International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering*. IEEE, 2010, pp. 111–120.
- [23] Y. Yamamoto, D. Miyamoto, and M. Nakayama, "Text-mining approach for estimating vulnerability score," in *2015 4th International Workshop on Building Analysis Datasets and Gathering Experience Returns for Security (BADGERS)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 67–73.
- [24] E. Aghaei, W. Shadid, and E. Al-Shaer, "Threatzoom: Hierarchical neural network for cves to cwes classification," in *International Conference on Security and Privacy in Communication Systems*. Springer, 2020, pp. 23–41.
- [25] V. Yosifova, A. Tasheva, and R. Trifonov, "Predicting vulnerability type in common vulnerabilities and exposures (cve) database with machine learning classifiers," in *2021 12th National Conference with International Participation (ELECTRONICA)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [26] Y. Pang, X. Xue, and H. Wang, "Predicting vulnerable software components through deep neural network," in *Proceedings of the 2017 International Conference on Deep Learning Technologies*, 2017, pp. 6–10.
- [27] R. Ferenc, P. Hegedűs, P. Gyimesi, G. Antal, D. Bán, and T. Gyimóthy, "Challenging machine learning algorithms in predicting vulnerable javascript functions," in *2019 IEEE/ACM 7th International Workshop on Realizing Artificial Intelligence Synergies in Software Engineering (RAISE)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 8–14.
- [28] I. Kalouptoglou, M. Siavvas, D. Kehagias, A. Chatzigeorgiou, and A. Ampatzoglou, "Examining the capacity of text mining and software metrics in vulnerability prediction," *Entropy*, vol. 24, no. 5, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/24/5/651>
- [29] I. Kalouptoglou, M. Siavvas, A. Ampatzoglou, D. Kehagias, and A. Chatzigeorgiou, "Software vulnerability prediction: A systematic mapping study," *Information and Software Technology*, p. 107303, 2023.
- [30] M. Siavvas, D. Kehagias, and D. Tzovaras, "A preliminary study on the relationship among software metrics and specific vulnerability types," in *2017 International Conference on Computational Science and Computational Intelligence (CSCI)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 916–921.
- [31] L. Wartschinski, Y. Noller, T. Vogel, T. Kehrer, and L. Grunke, "Vudenc: Vulnerability detection with deep learning on a natural codebase for python," *Information and Software Technology*, p. 106809, 2022.
- [32] L. Kong, S. Luo, L. Pan, Z. Wu, and X. Li, "A multi-type vulnerability detection framework with parallel perspective fusion and hierarchical feature enhancement," *Computers & Security*, p. 103787, 2024.
- [33] D. Zou, S. Wang, S. Xu, Z. Li, and H. Jin, "A deep learning-based system for multiclass vulnerability detection," *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 2224–2236, 2019.
- [34] C. Mamede, E. Pinconschi, R. Abreu, and J. Campos, "Exploring transformers for multi-label classification of java vulnerabilities," in *2022 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Software Quality, Reliability and Security (QRS)*, 2022, pp. 43–52.
- [35] A. Mazuera-Rozo, A. Mojica-Hanke, M. Linares-Vásquez, and G. Bavota, "Shallow or deep? an empirical study on detecting vulnerabilities using deep learning," in *2021 IEEE/ACM 29th International Conference on Program Comprehension (ICPC)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 276–287.
- [36] "Top programming languages that will rule in 2022," <https://fireart.studio/blog/top-programming-languages-that-will-rule-in-2021/>, accessed: 2024-03-20.
- [37] I. Kalouptoglou, M. Siavvas, D. Kehagias, A. Chatzigeorgiou, and A. Ampatzoglou, "An empirical evaluation of the usefulness of word embedding techniques in deep learning-based vulnerability prediction," in *EuroCybersec2021, Lecture Notes in Communications in Computer and Information Science*, 10 2021.
- [38] Y. Zhou, S. Liu, J. Siow, X. Du, and Y. Liu, "Devign: Effective vulnerability identification by learning comprehensive program semantics via graph neural networks," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.03496*, 2019.
- [39] Z. Li, D. Zou, S. Xu, X. Ou, H. Jin, S. Wang, Z. Deng, and Y. Zhong, "Vuldeepecker: A deep learning-based system for vulnerability detection," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1801.01681*, 2018.
- [40] L. Wolf, Y. Hanani, K. Bar, and N. Dershowitz, "Joint word2vec networks for bilingual semantic representations," *Int. J. Comput. Linguistics Appl.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 27–42, 2014.
- [41] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, Ł. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin, "Attention is all you need," in *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 2017, pp. 5998–6008.
- [42] Y. Zhu, R. Kiros, R. Zemel, R. Salakhutdinov, R. Urtasun, A. Torralba, and S. Fidler, "Aligning books and movies: Towards story-like visual explanations by watching movies and reading books," in *The IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, December 2015.
- [43] Y. Liu, M. Ott, N. Goyal, J. Du, M. Joshi, D. Chen, O. Levy, M. Lewis, L. Zettlemoyer, and V. Stoyanov, "Roberta: A robustly optimized bert pretraining approach," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.11692*, 2019.
- [44] A. F. de Araújo and R. M. Marcacini, "Re-bert: automatic extraction of software requirements from app reviews using bert language model," in *Proceedings of the 36th annual ACM symposium on applied computing*, 2021, pp. 1321–1327.
- [45] K. Kaur and P. Kaur, "Improving bert model for requirements classification by bidirectional lstm-cnn deep model," *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, vol. 108, p. 108699, 2023.
- [46] K. Huang, S. Yang, H. Sun, C. Sun, X. Li, and Y. Zhang, "Repairing security vulnerabilities using pre-trained programming language models," in *2022 52nd Annual IEEE/IFIP International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks Workshops (DSN-W)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 111–116.
- [47] "Explore the world of cyber security," <https://owasp.org/>, accessed: 2024-03-20.
- [48] L. Wartschinski, "Vudenc - python corpus for word2vec," Dec. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3559480>
- [49] "Understanding Micro, Macro, and Weighted Averages," <https://iamirmasoud.com/2022/06/19/understanding-micro-macro-and-weighted-averages-for-scikit-learn-metrics-in-multi-class-classification-with-example/>, accessed: 2024-02-10.
- [50] I. Kalouptoglou, M. Siavvas, A. Ampatzoglou, D. Kehagias, and A. Chatzigeorgiou, "Software Vulnerability Classification using Text Mining and Deep Learning Techniques," <https://sites.google.com/view/vulnerabilityclassification/>, Accessed: 2024-04-01.
- [51] L. Breiman, "Random forests," *Machine learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5–32, 2001.